

Strategies to Improve Youth Character in Maintaining Relationship between Chinese-Indonesian Culture

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Abstract

Strengthening character is one of the priority programs of President Joko Widodo and Vice President Jusuf Kalla. In his mind, it was stated that the government would revolutionize the nation's character. This study uses a decision support system that is used to select strategies that can be used to improve the character of young people in maintaining the relationship between Chinese-Indonesian culture. The research approach uses hierarchical analytical processes and multi-criteria decision making using expert choice applications. Both of these approaches are used because both approaches are often used in decision support systems, so it is expected to be used to determine strategies that can be used to improve the character of young people in maintaining relations between Chinese-Indonesian culture.

Penguatan karakter merupakan salah satu program prioritas Presiden Joko Widodo dan Wakil Presiden Jusuf Kalla. Dalam benaknya disebutkan bahwa pemerintah akan merevolusi karakter bangsa. Penelitian ini menggunakan sistem pendukung keputusan yang digunakan untuk memilih strategi yang dapat digunakan untuk meningkatkan karakter generasi muda dalam menjaga hubungan budaya Tionghoa-Indonesia. Pendekatan penelitian menggunakan proses analitis hierarkis dan pengambilan keputusan multi kriteria menggunakan aplikasi pilihan ahli. Kedua pendekatan tersebut digunakan karena kedua pendekatan tersebut sering digunakan dalam sistem pendukung keputusan, sehingga diharapkan dapat digunakan untuk menentukan strategi yang dapat digunakan untuk meningkatkan karakter generasi muda dalam menjaga hubungan budaya Tionghoa-Indonesia.

Keywords: *Analytical Hierarchy Process; youth character; experts choice; Indonesia; China*

Introduction

Law Number 20 the year 2003 Republic of Indonesia concerning the National Education System in Article 3 states that National education functions to develop capabilities and form a dignified national character and civilization to educate the life of the nation.¹ National education aims to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe and fear God Almighty, have a noble heart, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become a democratic and responsible citizen. This national education is also expected to be the main foundation for the success of improving the character of young people in maintaining relations between Chinese-Indonesian culture.²

Strengthening character is one of the priority programs of President Joko Widodo (Jokowi) and Vice President Jusuf Kalla from the Republic of Indonesia. In his mind, it was stated that the government would revolutionize the nation's character. Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia implements successive strengthening of national character through the Character Education Strengthening Movement which was launched since 2016.

In accordance with President Joko Widodo's direction, character education at the basic education level has a greater portion than education that teaches science. For elementary school, it is 70 percent, while for junior secondary schools it is 60 percent.³ Law Number 20 the 2003 Republic of Indonesia in Article 13 Paragraph 1 states that the education path consists of formal, non-formal, and informal education that can complement and enrich each other.⁴ Formal, non-formal, and informal education is institutions that contribute to achieving competence and character building for young people. However, the reality is that young people lack education from their parents, because of their parents' activities, and also because of a lack of understanding of parents in educating young people in the family environment.

Sari E. states that parents have the right to all education of their children but parents do not have the right to curb and take authoritarian children's rights.⁵ It is inconceivable that authoritarian parenting is bad for children's personal development, they will be indifferent, emotionally unresponsive, aggressive, insecure, always have negative views, unstable emotions, imbalanced emotions and intellectuals, and of course personality problems this will have an impact on the education of children in school.

Intercourse in the surrounding environment will also become an education that influences the formation of the character of young people. Print and electronic media will also have a negative influence on the formation of youth character. Sari E. reveals that society has a certain role in shaping children's

personalities.⁶ The cultural environment of various communities and family environments will influence children's thinking. In a cultural environment, young people interact with other communities, sometimes when they are in a culture of society that has behavior's and relationships that can direct young people to juvenile delinquency, have an egoistic attitude, have an attitude that must be respected, and show their existence to make them more prey to juvenile delinquency.

In wonosobozone.com, compared to the previous year, the number of juvenile delinquency in 2016 increased quite rapidly, which was more than 20%. The Head of Reproductive Health Subdivision, Office of Family Planning Population Control for Women's Empowerment and Child Protection, Nurul Hidayati, said this happened because of several factors, including environmental influences and gadgets. But Nurul believes that the biggest cause of this deviation is family involvement.⁷

The complexity in making decisions to improve the character of young people can be overcome by using a decision support system approach. This study uses a decision support system that is used to select strategies that can be used to improve the character of young people in maintaining the relationship between Chinese-Indonesian culture. The research approach uses analytical hierarchical processes and multi-criteria decision making using expert choice applications. Both of these approaches are used because both approaches are often used in decision support systems, so it is expected to be used to determine strategies that can be used to improve the character of the younger generation in maintaining relations between Chinese-Indonesian culture.

In accordance with the problem stated in the background above, the problem of how to provide comfort to all potential voters in determining strategies that can be used to improve the character of young people using several criteria so that decisions can be made, to build the best young generation according determined in maintaining the relationship between Chinese-Indonesian culture.

The purpose of this study is to be able to determine strategies that can be used to improve the character of young people in maintaining the relationship between Chinese-Indonesian culture and also can make effective decision support systems and multi-criteria decision making in accordance with the analytical hierarchy process method and use of expert choice 2000TM application.

Literature Review

Suyanto defines character as a way of thinking and behaving that characterizes each individual to live and work together, both in family, society, nation, and state. Character is a characteristic possessed by an object or individual.⁸ Kertajaya defines a character is a characteristic possessed by an object or individual. These characteristics are original and rooted in individual objects or personalities, and are machines that encourage how someone acts, behaves, speaks and responds to something.⁹

This character education can shape teenagers into achievements. In their educational achievements, they are taught religious values that describe good things so that adolescents grow as human beings who are sensitive to the social environment. In addition, they are also taught the tolerance value and the love of peace or human values that makeup teenagers to love, be virtuous and peaceful. In character education, they are also taught the value of working hard, creative, independent, and have a high curiosity that can make teenagers as achievers.¹⁰

In the history of the Chinese people, came to Indonesia for a long time. According to records in Chinese history, during the Han Dynasty (131 AD), there were official relations between the Han Dynasty in China and Yavadwipa in Indonesia. In the 7th century, the Tang Kingdom began to have cultural and Buddhist relations with the Sriwijaya Kingdom. in the 15th century during the Ming Dynasty, a Chinese Muslim Zhenghe led a row of ships three times to land in the Majapahit kingdom to establish trade and cultural relations. Since then many people of Chinese descent have begun to roam and settle on the islands.¹¹

Roger and Marek define a decision support system is an interactive computer-based system that assists users in assessment and selection.¹² This system not only provides data storage and retrieval but also increases traditional information access with support for decision-making and model-based reasoning.¹³

Decision making with many criteria is one of the most widely used methods in the field of decision making.¹⁴ The purpose of making several decision criteria is to choose the best alternative from several mutually beneficial alternatives based on general performance in various criteria determined by decision makers.^{15 16}

One model that can be used as a decision-making process is to use an analytical hierarchy process. The analytical hierarchy process was developed by Dr. Thomas L. Saaty from the Wharton School of Business in the 1970s to organize information and assessment in choosing the most preferred alternatives.^{17 18 19} The working principle of the analytical hierarchy process is as

follows.

- a. Compilation of hierarchies, namely the problem that must be solved is broken down into its elements, namely criteria and alternatives, then arranged into a hierarchical structure.
- b. Alternative criteria and assessments were assessed through pairwise comparisons. According to Saaty,²⁰ for various problems, a scale of 1 to 9 is the best scale in expressing opinions. The value and definition of qualitative opinion from the comparison scale from the following table.

Table 1. Saaty comparison scale^{23 24}

VALUE	DESCRIPTION
1	Criteria / Alternative A is as important as criteria / alternative B
3	A is slightly more important than B
5	A is clearly more important than B
7	A is clearly more important than B
9	A is really more important than B
2,4,6,8	If in doubt between two adjacent values

The value of comparison A with B is 1 (one) divided by the value of the ratio B with A.

- c. Priority Determination for each criterion and alternative, pairwise comparisons are needed. Relative comparison values are then processed to determine the relative rank of all alternatives. Both qualitative criteria and quantitative criteria can be compared according to predetermined judgment to produce weights and priorities. Weight or priority is calculated by matrix manipulation or through solving mathematical equations.
- d. Logical consistency for all elements is grouped logically and ranked consistently according to a logical criterion. Completion of the decision-making method with an analytical hierarchy process can use Expert Choice 2000TM software for calculating problem solving with an analytical hierarchy process that has been tested for reliability.

Research studies relevant to this study, Hermawan, concerning the Implementation of Community-Based Character Education in Student Exchange Activities at the Paesan Pekalongan Muhammadiyah Primary School,²⁵ concluded that the participation of the Kranggan Tersono community in exchange activities could be actively and attended. The equation with this research is research on character education. The difference with this research is that this study is about student exchange activities at the Paesan Pekalongan Muhammadiyah Elementary School. Nasrullah, on Character Education in Children and Youth,²⁶ concluded that the model of character education in adolescents aims to develop personality traits. The equation with this research

is research on character education. The difference with this study is that this study is about character education in children and adolescents.

Zulhijrah, on the Implementation of Character Education in Schools,²⁷ the character of the purpose of education has a very large effect on humans because it fits with the reality of human life and is very important in delivering them to be the noblest person in the world, people's eyes Allah SWT. The equation with this research is research on character education. The difference with this research is the application of character education in schools. Umagapi, on the Rise of Chinese-Indonesian Relations: Soft Power, Resources and Prospects in the Future,²⁸ concludes that cultural exchanges will also be the focus and tool for both countries to strengthen their cooperation. Indonesian students or Indonesian embassies must have active events such as Festival Indonesia. The equation with this research is research on Chinese-Indonesian relations. The difference with this research is about Soft Power, Resources, and Future Prospects.

Anggraini, on Teacher Strategies in Forming Student Characters According to 2013 Curriculum in Class 4 Ibtidaiyah Madrasah Nurul Huda Ngadirejo in Blitar City,²⁹ concluded that the teacher's strategy in shaping student character in accordance with the 2013 curriculum in the 4th grade was considered good. The equation with this research is research on character formation. The difference with this study is about the formation of student character in accordance with the 2013 curriculum in the 4th grade of Nurul Huda Ngadirejo Elementary School in Blitar City.

Dahniar, AW., about School Strategies in Forming Student Character at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri (MIN) Sukosewu Gandusari Blitar,³⁰ concluded that the efforts made by schools in shaping students' character were habituation. The equation with this research is research on character formation. The difference with this research is about the formation of student character at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri (MIN) Sukosewu Gandusari Blitar.

Sihombing, on Identifying Current Values from Indonesian Youth,³¹ concluded that there are 9 dimensions of Indonesian youth values: mutual cooperation, religion, democracy, kinship, friendliness, corruption, western culture, religious fanaticism, and selfishness. The equation with this study is research on young people. The difference with this research is about Identifying Current Values of Indonesian Youth. Panuntun, on Character Education Implementation through Dynamic Class Management,³² concluded that the implementation of character education through dynamic classroom management can shape student character values. The equation with this research is research on character education. The difference with this research is about dynamic class management.

Yanuardianto, concerning Child Character Education,³³ concluded that

character education is seen from its objectives in line. The equation with this research is research on character education. The difference with this research is about children's character education. Dewi, K., about the Teacher's Moral Assistance Strategy in Instilling Islamic Character Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTS) Students Guppi Samata Gowa,³⁴ concluded that Teacher's Strategy provides suggestions and motivation, examples, habituation, delivery of learning with lecture methods, assignments and punishments for students who break the rules or regulations at school. The equation with this research is research on the character. The difference with this research is about the Character of Islam Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTS) Guppi Samata Gowa. Syarifah, about Character Education for Class X Students at Aliyah Al Muttaqien Pancasila Sakti (Alpansa) Madrasah 2016/2017 Academic Year,³⁵ concluded that character education in class X students has been integrated with all intra-curricular and extra-curricular subjects. The equation with this research is research on character education. The difference with this research is about character education in class X students at Aliyah Al Muttaqien Pancasila Sakti (ALPANSa) Klaten Madrasah.

Faisal, decision support system for selecting data processing devices using Analytical Hierarchy Process and Multi-Critical Decision Making methods.³⁶ Decision Support Systems Selection of Image Processing Software with Multi-Criteria Criteria for Analytical Hierarchy Processes and Decision Making.³⁷ The equation is the use of the same approach, namely Analytical Hierarchy Process and Multi-Critical Decision Making. The difference in this research is the decision in choosing image processing software.

The conceptual framework of this study can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 1. Framework for The Concept of Thinking

The framework of thinking above illustrates the steps taken in this study: a) Research on improving the character of young people aims to obtain reasons, by looking for references through literature studies, interviews and discussions with expert respondents using focus group discussion methods. b) Then the process is continued at the next stage, which is to determine the research criteria using the method of focus group discussion. c) The next process determines alternative research. To avoid inconsistencies in making models, focus group discussions with expert respondents were conducted to determine the stages of making a valid model with elements that have a significant influence on the model. d) This method uses an iterative approach where attributes that are not feasible through the analysis process are removed so that the remaining attributes are attributes that are really important to investigate.

Methods

The research study began with field observations about improving the character of young people in maintaining the relationship between Chinese-Indonesian culture. This study uses descriptive analytical methods by presenting the results of interview summaries and survey results in the form of questionnaires. With this method, conditions for improving the character of young people will be explained, and an analysis of decisions to improve the character of young people will be carried out in maintaining the relationship between Chinese-Indonesian culture.

The next step is to look for secondary data in the field through various media, such as internet, literature and journals and articles so that accurate information is obtained about improving the character of young people. In addition, system identification is also carried out by considering supporting variables to improve the character of young people by conducting interviews and giving questionnaires to experts. This is an important stage because the model created must be accurate and accountable.

Based on the results of interviews with data experts and models, they were then processed using the Analytical Hierarchy Process approach to obtain results in the form of steps to be taken. Decisions must be immediately followed up in the form of actions or can also be reviewed by a decision if it turns out that the new information obtained can influence the results to reduce uncertainty, new decisions will be obtained. In this study data and information were collected from expert respondents using interview techniques in the Trilogi University campus environment. It is expected that after conducting this research so that prospective voters can make the right choice according to their choice.

The research begins with the process of collecting primary data through surveys and direct interviews in the field according to existing needs and conditions. And at the same time, the researchers also searched for secondary data obtained through literature studies, journals, and articles. The final stage of this research is to process the data that has been obtained with the multi-criteria decision-making approach and the analytical hierarchy process to formulate the 130 problem and get alternative rankings to be carried out when the multi-criteria decision-making method and analytical hierarchy process method will be applied. To determine priority steps to improve the character of young people in maintaining the relationship between Chinese-Indonesian culture, then on the criteria side there are 3 (three) criteria and 3 (three) strategic alternatives that support research on improving the character of young people in Indonesia, maintain the relationship between Chinese-Indonesian culture. Strategic criteria and alternatives can be determined in the table as follows.

Table 2. Criteria and alternatives for improving youth character

TARGET	CRITERIA	ALTERNATIVE
Improve Youth Character	Prevention	Residence; Education; Honesty
	Initial Adjustment Program	Residence; Education; Honesty
	After the Adjustment Program	Residence; Education; Honesty

The following shows a hierarchical graph and a decision to analyze the improvement in youth character:

Figure 2. Analytical Hierarchical Process Diagram

Expert choice 2000TM is software that can be used to calculate problem-solving with the multi-criteria decision-making process and the analytical hierarchy process. In this study data processing will use the expert choice 2000TM application which has been tested for reliability.

Results and Discussion

Weighting results in processing, analyzing, and interpreting data that influence the improvement youth character can be seen in the following details. The results of weighting processing, analysis and interpretation of data for research purposes to the improvement youth character can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 3. The improvement youth character chart

From the improvement youth character graph above, each weight value is obtained Prevention is 65.9%; After the Adjustment Program is 18.5%, and Initial Adjustments Program is 15.6%. The results of weighting processing, analysis, and interpretation of data for Prevention criteria can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 4. Prevention criteria chart

From the Prevention criteria chart above, each weight value is obtained Honesty is 60%; Residence is 20%, and Education is 20%. 132 Weighting results from processing, analysis, and interpretation of data for the Initial Adjustment Program criteria can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 5. Initial Adjustment Program criteria chart

From the Initial Adjustment Program criteria chart above are obtained with each weighted value Honesty is 50%; Education is 25%, and Residence is 25%. The results of weighting the processing, analysis, and interpretation of data for After the Adjustment Program criteria can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 6. After the adjustment program criteria chart

After the Adjustment Program criteria chart above, each weighted value Honesty is 60%; Education is 20%, and Residence is 20%. Weighting results from global processing, analysis, and interpretation of data can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 7. Global Weighting Chart

From the global weighing chart above, we get each weighing value Honesty is 58.2%; Education is 20.9%, and Residence is 20.9%.

Figure 8. Sensitivity Graphs Performance

Based on the performance of the sensitivity graph, it can be concluded that of the strategic alternatives if sorted, the sequence is the first Honesty; second Education; and third Residence. Inconsistency ratios data collected from expert respondents can be seen in the table below.

Table 3. Inconsistency ratios table

COMPARATIVE MATERIAL MATERIALS	CR VALUE
The target of research is to improve the character	0.03
Prevention criteria	0
Initial Adjustment Program criteria	0
After the Adjustment Program criteria	0
Global weighting	0.01

Inconsistency ratios table COMPARATIVE MATERIAL MATERIALS CR VALUE
 The target of research is to improve the character 0.03 Prevention criteria 0
 Initial Adjustment Program criteria 0 After the Adjustment Program criteria 0
 Global weighting 0.01 134 It can be concluded that the paired comparison given
 by expert respondents has an inconsistency ratio value that is smaller than 0.1
 as the maximum limit of the 0.01 inconsistency ratio value. Thus the results of
 combined geometric calculations from expert respondent data are quite
 consistent.

Conclusion

The results of processing data from expert respondents obtained when sorted were the first to choose Honesty with a weight of 58.2%; the second chose Education with a weight of 20.9%, and select the third Residence weighing 20.9%. The data inconsistency ratio is considered good because 0.01, is smaller than 0.1 as the maximum inconsistency ratio. In this study, the results obtained were to choose honesty by 58.2%, as a strategy that can be used to improve the character of young people in maintaining the relationship between ChineseIndonesian culture. The rest chose residential and education each at 20.9%. By conducting research to improve the character of young people in maintaining the relationship between Chinese-Indonesian culture, research on the Strategy of Improving Youth Character in Maintaining the Relationship between ChineseIndonesian Culture chose Honesty. It is hoped that this research can be a row model in the right strategy.

Endnotes

- ¹ Law Number 20 of 2003
- ² Law Number 20 of 2003 in Article 3
- ³ The Ministry of Education and Culture's Public Communication and Service Bureau
- ⁴ Law Number 20 of 2003 in Article 13 Paragraph 1
- ⁵ Sari, E., 2018, www.kumparan.com
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- ⁷ www.wonosobozone.com
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- ¹² Roger, R. Flynn, and Marek, J. Druzdzel. 2007
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- ³⁴ Dewi, K., 2017, UIN Makassar
- ³⁵ Syarifah, 2017, IAIN Surakarta
- ³⁶ Faisal, 2015, KNSI 2015, ISSN: 1907-9613
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